

Appendix 2: Reference Collection

This appendix contains photographs of reference hairs, which are hairs with a known identity that we compared to hairs collected in hair tubes for identification purposes. The photographs presented here are of hair bases, tips, medullae, and cuticle patterns. We present a single representative photograph of each of these sections of hair for each species. Hairs were photographed at either 200X or 400X magnification using an echo revolve brightfield microscope.

Species	Figure number	Length (mm) (maximum, average)	Shaft width (nm) (range, average)	Medulla width (nm) (range, average)	Medullary index (range, average)	Medulla description	Medulla broad category
White-footed mouse (<i>Peromyscus sp.</i>)	1	13, 7.235	14-45, 27.76	6-39, 21.12	0.4-0.9286, 0.7232	Ovate aggregations 1-3 abreast, almost entire shaft width, aggregations can be fused	A
House ouse (<i>Mus musculus</i>)	2	7, 5.667	38-43, 40.67	25-37, 31.33	0.6098-0.9737, 0.7759	Ovate aggregations 2-4 abreast, almost entire shaft width, aggregations can be fused	A or F
Northern short tailed shrew (<i>Blarina brevicauda</i>)	3	6, 5.7	17-30, 24.30	10-24, 16.8	0.5-0.8276, 0.6736	Wide, rectangular aggregations, never in multiple columns, almost	B

						entire shaft width	
Eastern mole (<i>Scalopus aquaticus</i>)	4	7, 5.909	24-44, 32.36	16-28, 23	0.6136-0.8065, 0.7186	Wide, rectangular aggregations, never in multiple columns, almost entire shaft width	B
Eastern meadow vole (<i>Microtus pennsylvanicus</i>)	5	13, 10	22-60, 45	7-49, 32.5	0.3182-0.8333, 0.6743	Ovate aggregations 4-6 abreast, almost entire midshaft width	A, B or F
Brown rat (<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>)	6	21, 17.33	59-80, 67.67	36-53, 42.67	0.5625-0.6625, 0.661	wide, thin aggregations, very dark	B or E
Black rat (<i>Rattus rattus</i>)	7 and 8	12, 7.786	14-137, 49.57	6-122, 40.86	0.4286-0.918, 0.7368	Juvenile hairs display circular aggregations 3-6 across; adult hairs usually display 8 circular aggregations across however underfurs of both stages have 1-2 aggregations	A, B or F

Eastern chipmunk (<i>Tamias striatus</i>)	9	19, 12.09	55-94, 71.36	40-78, 57.36	0.6557-0.8769, 0.7971	Dark column, 4- 5 circular or ovular vacuolations abreast, almost entire shaft width -sometimes appears like ovate aggs.	D or F
Eastern grey squirrel (<i>Sciurus carolinensis</i>)	10	15, 10.40	41-94, 68.50	30-82, 53.6	0.6056-0.8723, 0.7747	Dark column, 4- 8 circular or ovular vacuolations abreast, almost entire shaft width -sometimes appears like ovate aggs.	D or F
Virginia opossum (<i>Didelphis virginiana</i>)*	11	50 and 48	91 and 98	37 and 38	0.3878 and 0.4066	Appears vacuolated and ridged? Or irregular aggregations	D
Raccoon (<i>Procyon lotor</i>),*	12	45 and 46	93	46 and 47	0.4946 and 0.5054	Homogenous, dark column, approximately	E

						half of the shaft width	
Long-tailed weasel (<i>Mustela frenata</i>)	13	18, 12.6	69-91, 80.6	49-72, 61.4	0.7024-0.8415, 0.7597	irregular, aggregations wide and thin, varying numbers across	B
Stoat/Ermine (<i>Mustela erminea</i>)	14	10, 7	60-99, 79	46-83, 59.89	0.6986-0.8384, 0.7548	vaculations of irregular size and shape, usually oval or circular, 4-5 across	B
Striped skunk (<i>Mephitis mephitis</i>)*	15	77, one length unmeasured	108 and 112	76 and 38	0.7037 and 0.3393	Homogenous, dark column	E
American mink (<i>Neovison vison</i>)*	16	26 and 28	86 and 91	47 and 53	0.5465 and 0.5824	wide thin aggregations displaying occasional bulges	B
Fisher (<i>Pekania pennanti</i>)*	17	37 and 34	76 and 67	42 and 41	0.5526 and 0.6119	wide thin aggregations displaying occasional bulges	B

Peromyscus leucopus (white-footed mouse)

Figure 1. A: Tip of hair at 200X, B: Medulla of hair at 400X, C: Base of hair without intact follicle at 200X, D: Medulla of hair at 400X, E: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X

Mus musculus (house mouse)

Figure 2. A: Tip of hair at 200X, B: Section of hair medulla lacking pigment at 400X, C: Medulla of hair at 400X, D: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X

Blarina brevicauda (northern short-tailed shrew)

Figure 3. A: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X, B: Tip of hair at 200X, C: Base of hair without intact follicle at 200X, D: A hair stricture at 200X, E: Medulla of hair at 400X

Scalopus aquaticus (eastern mole)

Figure 4. A: Base of hair without intact follicle at 200X, B: Medulla of hair at 400X, C: Tip of hair at 200X, D: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X

Microtus pennsylvanicus (meadow vole)

Figure 5. A: Base of hair without intact follicle at 200X, B: Tip of hair at 200X, C: Medulla of hair at 400X, D: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X

Rattus norvegicus (Norway rat)

Figure 6. A: Base of hair without intact follicle at 200X, B: Tip of hair at 200X, C: Medulla of hair at 400X

Rattus rattus (black rat: juvenile)

Figure 7. A: Base of hair with intact follicle at 200X, B: Tip of hair at 200X, C: Medulla of hair at 400X

Rattus rattus (black rat: adult)

Figure 8. A: Base of hair with follicle intact at 200X, B: Tip of hair at 200X, C: Medulla of hair at 400X, D: Section of hair medulla lacking pigment at 400X

Tamias striatus (chipmunk)

Figure 9. A: Medulla of hair at 400X, B: Base of hair without intact follicle at 200X, C: Tip of hair at 200X, D: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X, E: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X

Sciurus carolinensis (grey squirrel)

Figure 10. A: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X, B: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X, C: Tip of hair at 200X, D: Medulla of hair at 400X, E: Base of hair without intact follicle at 200X

Didelphis virginiana (Virginia opossum)

Figure 11. A: Base of hair without intact follicle at 200X, B: Tip of hair at 200X, C: Medulla of hair at 400X.

Procyon lotor (raccoon)

Figure 12. A: Base of hair without intact follicle at 200X, B: Tip of hair at 200X, C: Medulla of hair at 400X, D: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X

Mustela frenata (Long-tailed weasel)

Figure 13. A: Base of hair without intact follicle at 200X, B: Tip of hair at 200X, C: Medulla of hair at 400X.

Mustela erminea (Stoat/Ermine)

Figure 14. A: Base of hair without intact follicle at 200X, B: Tip of hair at 200X, C: Medulla of hair at 400X.

Mephitis mephitis (Striped skunk)

Figure 15. A: Base of hair without intact follicle at 200X, B: Tip of hair at 200X, C: Unpigmented medulla of hair at 400X.

Neovison vison (American mink)

Figure 16. A: Base of hair without intact follicle at 200X, B: Tip of hair at 200X, C: Medulla of hair at 400X.

Pekania pennanti (Fisher)

Figure 17. A: Tip of hair at 200X, B: Base of hair without intact follicle at 200X, C: Medulla of hair at 400X.